

A Theorem on the Annamalai's Binomial Identities

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Abstract: This paper presents an algorithmic technique to establish a theorem on the Annamalai's binomial identities. The binomial theorem and its computing technique refer to a sort of methodological advances that is useful for researchers working in computation, science, engineering, and management.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10

Keywords: computation, combinatorics, binomial theorem

1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations [1] of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind for establishing a combinatorial geometric series [1-3] and an innovative binomial coefficient [4] shown below:

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3)\dots(r+n-1)(r+n)}{n!},$$

where $n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ denotes the combinatorial geometric series V_r^n the innovative binomial coefficient.

Let us compare the binomial coefficient V_x^y with the traditional binomial coefficient [4, 5] as follows:

Let $z = x + y$. Then, $\binom{z}{x} = zC_x = \frac{z!}{x!y!}$. Here, $V_x^y = V_y^x \Rightarrow zC_x = zC_y, (x, y, z \in N)$.

For example, $V_3^5 = V_5^3 = (5+3)C_3 = (5+3)C_5 = 56$.

Also, $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = \frac{n!}{n!0!} = 1$ and $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1 (\because 0! = 1)$.

Note that the geometric series $\sum_{i=0}^n x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^0 x^i$ is also a combinatorial geometric series.

2. Binomial Theorem

A binomial theorem [7] is constituted using the Annamalai's binomial identities [6-9] given below:

(i) $V_n^0 = V_0^n = 1$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

(ii) $V_r^m = V_m^r, \quad (m, r \geq 1 \ \& \ m, r \in N)$.

(iii) $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1} \quad (OR) \quad \sum_{i=0}^r V_n^i = V_{n+1}^r, \quad (\because V_r^m = V_m^r \ \& \ V_n^0 = V_0^n = 1)$.

Theorem:
$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = V_{r+1}^{n+1} - 1.$$

Proof.
$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 = V_r^1; \quad \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 = V_r^2; \quad \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 = V_r^3; \quad \dots; \quad \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = V_r^{n+1}.$$

By adding these expressions on the both sides, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} V_r^i$$

Here,
$$\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} V_r^i = V_r^0 + \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} V_r^i - V_r^0 = \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} V_r^i - 1 = V_{r+1}^{n+1} - 1, (\because V_r^0 = 1).$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^0 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^1 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^2 + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^3 + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n = V_{r+1}^{n+1} - 1.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Note that
$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_0^i + \sum_{i=0}^r V_1^i + \sum_{i=0}^r V_2^i + \sum_{i=0}^r V_3^i + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^r V_n^i = V_{n+1}^{r+1} - 1.$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem on the Annamalai's binomial identities was introduced. This binomial theorem refers to a sort of methodological advance that is useful to researchers who are working in science, engineering, and medicine [10].

References

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